

Phonological Error Analysis in Reading Arabic Texts by Ninth Grade Students at the Wustha Level, Nurus Salam Islamic Boarding School, Mentayan, Bantan Subdistrict, Bengkalis Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study attempts to identify the causes that led to the phonological mistakes of the stressing side, pauses, tones, and intonations in the Arabic text read by students at the Nurus Salam Mentayan Resident House's 9th grade Wustha level. The error analysis approach is used in this investigation to track the development of Arabic text reading abilities. In addition to recording techniques, freely engaged dialectical methods and observation are used in data collection. The study's findings demonstrated 50 errors in the stressed speech in both the speech and the sentence. The pause happened when one spoke the ma`rifat phrases in a sentence or number when one spoke the word Qaul and the phrase that came from it, and when one spoke the words and responses. 43 reading tones do not match the word's meaning; 4) 32 intonations on the intonation tune do not match the sentence or number's context. Since intonations are uttered consistently without regard to meaning, they cannot convey the structure and meaning of numbers. Several variables contribute to the incidence of mistakes, such as: 1) When it comes to suprasegmental sounds, particularly stressing, pauses, tones, and intonation, teachers pay insufficient attention to them. 2) In theory, no subjects like ashwat can accept the super-segmental sound element. 3) The mother tongue heavily impacts the use of this suprasegmental noise, as the students' reading habits of Indonesians are also flat, meaning they ignore tone, intonation, stressing, and pauses.

KEYWORDS: Arabic phonology, mistakes, emphasis, pauses, tones, and intonation

INTRODUCTION

A subfield of linguistics called phonology studies human sounds. A clear and acceptable message is conveyed in a well-trusted statement that the listener can easily understand. Pronunciation correctness matters because it impacts the meaning conveyed by the speaker. The science of phonology is the first thing that Arabic language learners, in particular, need to acquire to pronounce letters, verbs, phrases, and sentences correctly. It is certain that if the student needs to study phonetics first, there will be several challenges and mistakes in applying language skills during the learning process, mainly when speaking and reading. These include emphasising pronunciation, tone, intonation, or pauses in both letters and phonologies, words, and phrases that can affect semantic meaning and applying speaking and reading skills. Subsequently, it became evident that studying Arabic phonology was crucial to pronouncing the language by the standards and elocution of native Arabic speakers.

This study examines phonological faults in Arabic that occur in stressing, tone, intonation, and pauses. After the sound is captured, these errors are described, and further analysis is done on errors that occur at the level of a proverb, word, clause, or sentence. Sentences like (مَكَاتِهِمْ عَلَى قُرَاهُمْ) indicate that Muhammad reads the book. The speaker emphasises that Muhammad reads, not writes or speaks. However, when the speaker emphasises the word (كِتَابًا), the listener finds it challenging to understand the meaning quickly and may even misunderstand it. Error on the side of the pause (+), for instance: (الْجَدِيدُ + الْمَمْلُوكُ مُدْرَةٌ) (the new school head), (الْجَدِيدُ + مُدْرَةٌ). If a pause like the example is present, it indicates (Kepala sekolah di sekolah yang baru). Additionally, certain words have faults in their tone and intonation, like this one: (غَائِبٌ مُحَمَّدٌ). If the speaker is saying that Muhammad is not present, the word should be pronounced with a moderate at the beginning, a high in the middle of the phrase, and a low at the conclusion.¹

The goal of the Qira'atul Kitab material, which should be focused on understanding the text of the Turats (classic) and understanding others, becomes branched towards improving the phonologic side of reading the students. It is based on observations made on the Qira'atul Kitab Santri of Class IX of Wustha at the Ph.D. Nurus Salam Mentayan, these phonological errors often occur when reading Arabic text. Even now, some struggle to differentiate and pronounce sounds correctly according

¹ . Ibid, hal 132.

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to phonology theory, whether in terms of makhrāj or nature, particularly when correctly adjusting stressing, pausing, or intonation. It makes it challenging to learn how to read Arabic texts. While reading comprehension is the most crucial ability in the training field, it also serves as the foundation of Nurus Salam Mentayan's exceptional program. Because the scholars in this area have done little research, the study concentrates on the phonological analysis of language faults from the stressing, pause, and intonation sides. This study aims to clarify stressing mistakes, pauses, tones, and intonations in phonological errors when reading Arabic texts and the circumstances that led to these errors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative descriptive research design, analysing data without resorting to numerical analysis in order to arrive at conclusions. Since the data being used is verbal student pronunciation while reading Arabic material in the Turats book content analysis is employed in the design process. Content analysis is also employed since it describes the sort of phonological mistakes that are made when reading the Arabic language text that is being read.

In terms of the data collecting method, the investigator observes how the speakers (informants) use language to determine the realisation of certain phonemes. This involves not only hearing the sounds the informant produces, but also seeing how the sound is made. Then, the recording approach is a supplement to the observation activity; that is, the recorded may be compared to the final recording, reevaluating the recorded data so that it can be verified using the obtained record files. To measure the development in acquiring Arabic-language reading abilities, the researchers employed error analysis techniques in their data analysis. They recorded and categorised the reading errors made by the students in order to reach a conclusion.

Eleven pupils from class IX at Wustha Pondok Pesantren Nurus Salam Mentayan Bantan area of Bengkalis are the topic of this research. The average class IX group is a students whose level of competence reading the yellow book is above the ability of the other classes that exist in the Nurus Salam Training House, either the 'Ulya' class above it or the wustha class below it. Purposive sampling is a sample determination technique with this specific consideration. Thus, it has been selected as the focus of our investigation. This research was conducted in the Pondok Pesantren Nurus Salam Mentayan area of Bengkalis during the teaching year 2022–2023, namely from April 23, 2022, until September 10, 2022.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study students on the investigation of Suprasegmental sound, which refers to the sound that accompanies the segmental sound. These aspects include phonological faults in An-Nabr (stress/pressure), Al-Mufashal (jeda or persarticulation), Al-Nagmah (nada), or At-Tan-ghim (intonation). After being first displayed in error form, the data is then recorded in table form to provide a detailed explanation of the error. The table is constructed using data from 11 respondents who participated in the study. These respondents were selected from class IX students and their mistakes were analysed according to a certain pattern. The data descriptions in this study are categorised into 11 groups, each of which is segmented based on its phonological faults. Each table consists of four columns: the first column displays the error number, the second column shows the word type or centrally uttered sentence, the third column provides an explanation of the phonological mistake in terms of supra-segmental elements, and the fourth column indicates the error categorisation. The phonological faults in reading the Arabic text of Santri class IX level wustha at Pondok Pesantren Nurus Salam in Mentayan, Bantan district, Bengkalis, can be analysed as follows:

No	Name	Number of Errors An-Nabr (Stress/ Tekanan)	Number of Errors Al-Mufashal (Jeda Atau Persendian)	Number of Errors An-Nagmah (Nada)	Number of Error At-Tan-ghim (Intonasi)
1	Dimas Prayogi	8	3	1	1
2	Rosyidatul Ulya	3	2	3	3
3	Vila Sufiarni	7	1	7	3
4	Fitria Ningsih	3	1	6	3
5	Haikal Efendi	5	3	3	0
6	M. Farhan Nasution	4	3	4	4
7	M. Irfan Muhaimin	5	3	4	2
8	Nora Amelia	7	2	6	4
9	Nur Arini Fasya	4	2	4	6
10	Usni Farhan	2	3	3	3
11	Wibowo Rizqullah	2	3	2	3
Total		50	26	43	32

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The conclusion drawn from the data in the observation table and the recorded students readings is that, on average, the student has demonstrated proficient and fluent reading skills. It can be attributed to their daily practice of reading books under the guidance of subject teachers. Additionally, they understand the texts they read well, although occasional errors in grammar or calculation may occur due to a lack of attentiveness or focus. However, when it comes to suprasegmental sounds or elements accompanying phonemes, such as vocal pressure, word and sentence intervals, tone, and intonation, many of the 11 students still need help applying them correctly. They need proper training and attention from both the students and the teachers, which ultimately hampers their ability to read Arabic texts with perfection.

Based on the observations and analysis shown in the table above, it has been identified that there is an error in the application of suprasegmental sounds in reading Arabic text by the 11 students of class IX level Wustha Pondok Pesantren Nurul Salam Mentayan Prefecture, formerly part of the Bengkalis district.:

1) Phonological mistake in spelling An-Nabr related to stress or pressure.

The table above displays 50 instances when the application of the nabr pattern is erroneous. The accuracy of verb placement and word spelling inside a phrase could be more precise. The error has remained the same meaning, but it has affected the disappearance of the character and essence of the Arabic language. The word or phrase is said following the pattern or style of the Indonesian or Javanese language, resulting in a weak and horizontal pronunciation. No emphasis or stress is placed on one word in relation to another. These mistakes are categorised as follows:

- (a) There is no grammatical pressure (an-Nabr) on similar terms to the word *النظافة، أحكام، اصطلاحاً، أنواع، تستباح، الطهارة، كتاب الطهارات*. When words consist of short and long verbs or only long verbs, the emphasis is placed on the long verb after the word. Abraham stated that an-Nabr, which refers to pressure, measures the force applied to articulate a single word to enhance its audibility relative to other words.²
- (b) The words *أله، بصر، كان، و* do not have any diacritical marks (an-Nabr) indicating pressure. When a word consists of a single phrase or a short term, emphasise the term to highlight its essential nature through vocal expression or by emphasizing the beginning of the term.³
- (c) The word "shrimp" is not subject to phonetic stress (an-Nabr). When a word ends with a connected pronoun, the stress falls on the syllable preceding the last one if it is lengthy. If the text is brief, emphasise the third term of the stop word.⁴
- (d) There are no restrictions on disclosing the volume of water that can be utilised for publishing purposes, as well as the quantity of water utilised for publishing and other activities. Words that function as the subject of a sentence or phrases that relate to the quantity of something should be emphasised. The word alone cannot exert pressure, but the word that signifies the predicate carries the most force as it is the central element conveying the meaning or significance of the sentence or proposition.⁵

2) Identifying phonological mistakes in the al-Mufashal orthography The jeda serves the linguistic role of delimiting meanings by establishing gaps between groups of phrases in different places, influencing their respective meanings. This is evident in the mistakes shown below:

- (a) There should be no interruption when uttering the righteous word or the number of words. However, there should be a gap in the discourse between the *mubtada* and the *rumour* if both are *ma`rifat*. When there is no interruption, it signifies that the subject in question is the one who reverts to the preceding phrase.⁶
- (b) There is no pause between the sentence *Qaul* and its derived sentence in the phrase *منها قولهم: فعل ما تستباح به الصلاة* ('he did what allows the prayer'). The pause should be *قول* and its derivative *فعل ما تستباح به الصلاة*.
- (c) There is no pause between the condition and the result in the sentence or phrase *ولما كان الماء آلة للطهارة استطرده المصنف لأنواع المياه* ('and since water is a means of purification, the author digressed to discuss the types of water'). The pause should be between the result *استطرده* and the previous sentence.⁷ In the table above, the researcher found 26 instances of the expression 'Al-Mufashal' errors (Pause or Segment).

3) Discovered phonological faults in the An-Nagmah (Nada) Arabic, where tone alterations impact the meaning of words. In the realm of intonation, the high tone holds significant importance. Lexical semantics is concerned with the determination of the meaning of a word or phrase. Utilising tone when reading is of utmost importance as it serves to differentiate meaning. The researchers discovered 43 instances in which the term did not align with its intended meaning or lacked tonal variation, among

² . Badri, Kamal Ibrahim. *Ilmu Lughah al Mubaramaj*. Saudi Arabiyah. Imadat Syabauni al Maktab-Jama'tu Malik Su'ud-Riyad, 1982. Hal. 5-6

³ . Jauhar, Nasruddin Idris, 2014, *Fonologi Bahasa Arab untuk Penutur Indonesia*, Sidoarjo: Lisan Arabi, h. 140-141

⁴ . Ibid.

⁵ . Ibid.

⁶ . Jauhar, Nasruddin Idris, 2014, *Fonologi Bahasa Arab untuk Penutur Indonesia*, h. 143-146

⁷ . Ibid.

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other discrepancies. a) The tone is monotonous in accurately stating the appropriate number of equations, not to mention that this line serves as the title of the reading text: "الطهارة كتاب". The conclusion of an ideal number of words should conclude with a subdued tone that is devoid of any emotional expression.⁸

- 4) Found a phonological error in the At-Tanghim dialect (Intonation) Teachers' neglect of suprasegmental sounds, such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonations, while listening to students' reading. The focus is solely on analysing segmental sounds, such as makhraj, mad, syllabus, grammar, and meaning, without considering stress, pause, tone, and intonation.

In theory, no topics address the issue of suprasegmental sound constituents like Ashwat science. However, when reading text, many linguistic aspects, such as segments, vocabulary, and grammar, are accompanied by suprasegmental elements like emphasis, pauses, tones, and intonations, which contribute to the overall oral delivery of the discourse. Inaccurate utilisation of prosodic features, including stress patterns, pauses, tones, and intonations, when reading texts such as news articles or scientific reports can result in communication breakdowns and hinder comprehension of the conveyed information. Hence, a genuine reader must possess knowledge, expertise, and awareness of accentuated patterns, breaks, inflexions, and cadences.

The use of this suprasegmental sound is prone to errors, which are heavily impacted by the speaker's home tongue. This is because speakers of Indonesian often read with a flat language style, neglecting to pay attention to aspects such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonation.

- 1) Teachers often neglect suprasegmental sounds, such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonations, while listening to students' reading. Instead, they tend to focus solely on analysing segmental sounds, such as makhraj, mad, syllables, grammar, and meaning, without giving due attention to stress, pause, tone, and intonation.
- 2) In theory, no topics address the issue of suprasegmental sound constituents like Ashwat science. However, while reading text, several components of language, including segmental elements (such as individual sounds), lexical elements (such as words), and grammar, are accompanied by super-segmental elements such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonations. These super-segmental factors contribute to the overall structure and flow of oral pronunciation. Inaccurate application of prosodic features, such as stress patterns, pauses, tones, and intonations, in specific contexts like news readings or polar currents can result in communication breakdowns and hinder message comprehension. Hence, a genuine reader must possess knowledge, expertise, and awareness towards emphasising patterns, pauses, tones, and intonations.
- 3) The use of this suprasegmental sound is prone to errors, which are significantly impacted by the speaker's home tongue. This is because speakers tend to read Indonesian with a flat language style, neglecting the importance of stress, pauses, tones, and intonation.

CONCLUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION

1. The 9th Grade students of Wustha Pondok Pesantren Nurus Salam Mentayan has identified phonological errors in stressing, pauses, tones, and intonations when reading Arabic texts. Specifically, a significant phonological error in the An-Nabr speech (stress/pressure) occurs approximately 50 times, indicating a lack of accuracy in applying the nabr pattern. A sentence's accuracy depends on the verb's location and the words' spelling. The error has not entirely and potentially changed its meaning, but it has influenced the vanishing of the essence and nature of the Arabic language. The word or phrase is said following the pattern or style of the Indonesian or Javanese language, resulting in a weak and horizontal pronunciation. No emphasis or stress is placed on one word in relation to another.
2. A phonological fault in the spacing between phrase groups in different places might impact the meaning. The mistake arises while referring to the phrase or numeral positioned between the term "Qaul" and the subsequent term, as well as between the terms and their corresponding responses. The researchers discovered a total of 26 erroneous phrases throughout the analysis of the error.
3. The researchers discovered 43 instances on the An-Nagmah (Nada) note where the readings did not correspond to the word's intended meaning or lacked the appropriate tone. When pronouncing the ideal number of euphemisms, it is essential to avoid a monotone delivery and instead convey them with a low tone devoid of emotion.
4. At At-Tan-ghim (Intonation), the researchers identified 32 intonations that were inconsistent with the context of the sentence or number. Their reading intonation cannot convey the structure and meaning of the number, as it is said with a monotonous tone and without any emphasis that highlights its significance. To convey the sentence's accurate structure and intended meaning, it is essential to employ a downward intonation precisely on the final syllable.
5. The factors that led to the development of phonological mistakes, such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonation, when reading Arabic text at the students of Class IX level Wustha Pondok Pesantren Nurus Salam Mentayan, include: 1) During the process of reading, the teacher ignores suprasegmental sounds, particularly stress, pauses, tones, and intonation. Instead, the focus is solely on analysing segmental sounds such as makhraj, mad, and grammar and meaning without considering the significance

⁸ . Ibid.

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of stress patterns, pauses, tone, and intonation. The mother tongue significantly impacts the use of suprasegmental sounds since the reading habits of Indonesian speakers often neglect the aspects of stress, pauses, tones, and intonation, resulting in errors.

Researchers suggest that teachers who teach yellow books or Arabic should focus on suprasegmental sounds, such as stress, pauses, tones, and intonations while reading or reciting. They should also pay attention to segmental sounds, such as makhrāj, mad, chalk, grammar, and meaning. In linguistics, it is crucial to offer disciplines that address the issue of suprasegmental sound aspects, such as Ashwat science. This is particularly significant for the development of Arabic speaking and reading skills.

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